

Microbiological, Radiographic and HRCT Correlation in Lower Lobe TuberculosisKavitha K¹, Geetha S H², Dayananda Kumar R³, Puneet Shirbur⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Akash Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Under Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Chikkaballapura Institute of Medical Sciences, Aruru village, Peresandra Post, Chikkaballapur, Karnataka, India³Professor & HOD, Department of Radiology, MVJ Medical College & Research Hospital, Dandupalya, 30th KM Milestone, National Highway 75, Kolathur P.O., Hoskote Taluk, Bengaluru Rural District, Under Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India⁴Associate professor, Department of Radiology, MVJ Medical College & Research Hospital, Dandupalya, 30th KM Milestone, National Highway 75, Kolathur P.O., Hoskote Taluk, Bengaluru Rural District, Under Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Tuberculosis confined to the lower lung fields often masquerades as pneumonic consolidation and the correct diagnosis gets delayed. Early diagnosis and treatment helps in the prevention of complications, a proper understanding of clinical, radiological features as well as treatment outcome of this disease entity is of crucial importance.**Material and Methods:** The study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Bangalore for a period of one year from January 2017 to February 2018. Data collection was prospective. 20 consecutive cases of lower lung tuberculosis were identified. 12 were males. 8 were females.**Results:** Main radiological presentation was patchy opacities seen in 9 of patients, homogeneous consolidation seen in 7 of patients, cavitation was seen in 3 of patients, nodular opacities in 2.**Conclusion:** The radiographic findings in lower lung field TB differ significantly from upper lobe disease. The most frequent radiographic finding is consolidation, more confluent and extensive than that found in upper lobes TB. Cavitory lesions are also frequently seen, which may be single or multiple and may lie within an area of consolidation.**Keywords:** Lower lobe, Tuberculosis, HRCT, Consolidation.

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Introduction

Lower lung field tuberculosis is defined as tuberculous disease found below an imaginary line traced across the hila and including the parahilar regions on a standard posterior-anterior chest x-ray without concomitant involvement of upper lobe. Anatomically, this includes the right middle lobe and lingula, in addition to the lower lobes. Lower lung field tuberculosis is an atypical presentation of pulmonary tuberculosis which often causes confusion in diagnosis. HIV/AIDS epidemic has considerably increased its incidence.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology and Department of Radiodiagnosis, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Bangalore for a period of 1 year from January 2017 to

February 2018. Data collection was prospective. A computer assisted search of all the reports of chest PA radiographs and CT thorax with the diagnosis of tuberculosis was conducted within the departmental database. Approval was obtained by institutional review board. Patient informed consent was waived.

All CT examinations were performed with 16-slice MDCT scanner (GE Brivo 385, Milwaukee, USA). The imaging parameters for the scout film and the scan are as follows. The parameters are: Scout KVp 120, mA 10 WW/WL: 500/50. Scan kVp 120, mA 120, and Interval 20 mm, thickness: 1.25mm, rotation time 1s, FOV, pitch & speed 1.375:1/13.75, ISO: 1.3s.ww/wl:50/150. Images were acquired and analyzed on the GE advantage workstation. The

images were archived using Magnetic optic discs and external hard drives.

The examination results were interpreted by two experienced radiologists each with more than five years of experience in interpreting Chest Radiographs and Thoracic CT examinations. Each scan was evaluated for location, number of opacities, nodules, segmental, lobar distribution calcification, lymphadenopathy, contrast enhancement and other associated lesions. All scans were interpreted in lung window settings. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS software 17.0. Quantitative variables were expressed as percentages.

Diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis was made by detailed clinical history, chest X-ray, examination of sputum for AFB by Ziehl-Neelsen method and its culture on Lowenstein-Jensen media. Patients whose sputum was negative for AFB by direct smear on three consecutive days and also by culture were diagnosed as cases of sputum negative pulmonary tuberculosis.

They were also confirmed on the basis of suggestive radiological findings and clinico-radiological non-responsiveness to a 2-3 weeks course of antibiotics. An arbitrary horizontal line across the hila in a posteroanterior (PA) chest film was taken as the dividing line between upper and lower lung fields. Para hilar regions were considered in lower lung fields.

Lower lung field included middle lobe and the lingula in addition to the lower lobes. Patients excluded from the study comprised cases of either ipsilateral or contralateral involvement of both upper and lower lung fields, pleural effusion and thickening unless associated with parenchymal lesions in the involved area. Having obtained informed consent, HIV testing was done in each

patient with pulmonary tuberculosis according to Center for Disease Control guidelines. All patients underwent a short course chemotherapy according to WHO guidelines.

Results

A total of 283 (180 males and 103 females) were diagnosed clinically as having tuberculosis. 141 patients (79 males and 63 females) were diagnosed as radiologically positive tuberculosis. 20 consecutive cases of lower lung tuberculosis were identified. 12 (60%) were males. 08 were females.

Various risk factors noted in the study were Diabetes seen in 09 patients, 07 were elderly, 10 were alcoholics, 6 had previous history of pulmonary tuberculosis and 3 were HIV positive cases.

Out of 141 radiologically positive cases, 57 had respiratory symptoms in the form of cough and scanty expectoration, 45 had mild to moderate grade fever, 32 had weight loss, 6 had pleuritic pain, 9 had hemoptysis.

Sputum smear for AFB was positive in 33 cases, 9 cases had BAL positive for AFB, 12 cases were diagnosed based on CT findings suggestive of TB and 6 were sputum negative and had unresolving pneumonia which improved on treatment.

Main radiological findings were patchy opacities seen in 27 of patients, homogeneous consolidation seen in 21 of patients, cavitation was seen in 10 of patients, nodular opacities in 7. 6 patients had para pneumonic effusion. 27 had right lung involvement, 24 had left lower lobe involvement, 9 had bilateral involvement. Right lung was more frequently affected in 23 patients. Left lung was involved in 20 and bilateral involvement in five patients.

Table 1: Findings on Chest Radiographs

Radiological findings	Number of patients
Patchy opacities	9
Homogenous consolidation	7
Cavitation	3
Nodules	2
Effusion	6
Bronchiectasis	6

Table 2: Findings on Thoracic CT

Findings	Number of patients
Centrilobular nodules	12
Linear branching opacities	10
Interlobular septal thickening	6
Poorly defined nodules	4
Lobular consolidation	7

The findings on thoracic CT were centrilobular nodules in 12 patients, linear branching opacities in 10 patients, interlobular septal thickening in 6 patients, poorly defined nodules in 4 and lobular consolidation in 7 cases.

Discussion

In persons with normal immune function, radiologic manifestations can be logically categorized into the two distinct forms of primary and post primary disease that develop in individuals without and with prior exposure and acquired specific immunity. Lymphadenopathy is the radiologic hallmark of primary TB. While enlarged nodes occur in 83%–96% of pediatric cases [1-3] the prevalence of lymphadenopathy decreases with increasing age [2]. The right para tracheal and hilar stations are the most common sites of nodal involvement in primary TB, although any combination, including bilateral hilar or isolated mediastinal lymphadenopathy, may also occur [2,3,4].

Parenchymal opacities occur in association with and affect the same side as nodal enlargement in approximately two thirds of pediatric cases of primary TB [2]. Opacities in primary pulmonary TB appear as an area of homogeneous consolidation [2, 5, 6], although patchy, linear [1] nodular [7], and mass like [8, 20] forms are also seen. Consolidation occurs in a segmental or lobar distribution. Multifocal involvement is seen radiographically in 12%–24% and found at autopsy in 16% of the affected cases [2, 6]. Common sites of parenchymal involvement in primary TB are upper [1], lower [6] or no regional predominance [2,5]. Obstructive atelectasis and over inflation are reported to occur in 9%–30% and 1%–5% of children with primary TB, respectively (1, 2). Consolidation of lower lung zones (10, 16) and normal findings (9, 10) are other atypical radiographic patterns associated with endobronchial TB. The prevalence of effusion increases with age and is reported to be 6%–11% in children [1, 2] and 29%–38% in adults [11, 5].

Parenchymal opacities in the apical and posterior segments of the upper lobes and the superior segment of the lower lobes with cavitation are the characteristic radiographic manifestations of post primary TB. An atypical pattern with opacities in the anterior segment of the upper lobes or basilar segments of the lower lobes are reported to occur in 5% of cases of post primary TB [6,12,13] Prior reports [14,15,16] suggesting that patients with diabetes mellitus and the elderly are predisposed to atypical distributions of post primary disease have not been confirmed with subsequent case control studies [17,18]. Parenchymal involvement in post primary TB manifests radiographically as heterogeneous opacities. An ill-defined area of

increased opacity associated with nodular and linear components is seen radiating from the hilum or in the periphery of the lung [19, 20]. With disease progression, additional opacities develop that may coalesce and distort adjacent bronchovascular and mediastinal structures [19,20]. In 3%–6% of cases of postprimary disease, solitary or multiple tuberculomas are the predominant parenchymal manifestation [7, 20, and 21]. Cavitation in single or multiple sites is seen radiographically in 40%–45% of cases of postprimary TB (6, 22). Walls of cavities may be thin and smooth to thick and nodular (6, 22). Air-fluid levels are reported to occur in 9%–21% of tuberculous cavities [6,22].

Bronchogenic spread of disease occurs when an area of caseous necrosis liquefies and communicates with the bronchial tree. Radiographically, it is identified in 20% of cases of postprimary TB (50) and manifests as multiple ill-defined 5- to 10-mm nodules in a segmental or lobar distribution, distant from the site of cavity formation and involving the lower lung zones [23,24,25].

On CT scans, bronchogenic spread of infection can be identified in 95% of persons with postprimary TB [24, 26]. According to Im and colleagues [24,27], the most common CT findings of bronchogenic spread are 2 to 4 mm centrilobular nodules and sharply marginated linear branching opacities [27,28]. Other findings include 5- to 8-mm poorly defined nodules, lobular consolidation and interlobular septal thickening [27]. Endobronchial involvement occurs in approximately 2%–4% of persons with pulmonary TB [8, 9]. Main, upper and lower lobe bronchi account for three-quarters of the involved sites [8]. On CT scans, endobronchial TB typically manifests as irregular or smooth circumferential bronchial narrowing associated with mural thickening [29, 30]. Hilar and mediastinal lymphadenopathy are uncommon manifestations of postprimary TB [6].

Tuberculous pleural effusion, a manifestation of primary disease may occur with postprimary disease in up to 19% of detected cases [31]. Pleural effusion is seen in 16%–18% of persons with postprimary TB and is typically unilateral [6, 13, 31]. Although parenchymal abnormalities are common findings, the ruptured parenchymal focus may be radiographically occult [32]. Occasionally, an air-fluid level may be demonstrable within the pleural cavity, indicating the presence of a bronchopleural fistula [6, 13]. Contrast-enhanced CT evaluation of postprimary tuberculous effusions typically reveals smooth thickening of visceral and parietal pleural surfaces separated by a variable amount of fluid (33, 34). Detection of persistent fluid within a calcified fibrothorax at CT should

raise concern for active disease and chronic tuberculous empyema [6, 13].

The utility of CT in the differentiation of active from inactive TB has been investigated in two case-control studies (26, 36). In the larger study by Lee et al (36), thin-section CT findings identified in 89 patients with active disease included centrilobular branching linear opacities (92%), lobular consolidation (62%), acinar nodule (61%), cavity (36%), and ground-glass attenuation (35%). These same findings were also observed in 95%, 35%, 47%, 22%, and 22% of the 57 patients with inactive disease, respectively [36]. In the study by Hatipoglu and colleagues [26], centrilobular nodules, tree-in-bud appearance, nodules 5–8 mm in diameter and consolidation were found in 91%, 71%, 69%, and 14% respectively of 32 patients with active disease and in none of 34 patients with inactive disease. The characteristic radiographic findings of miliary TB consist of innumerable, 1–3-mm, noncalcified nodules scattered throughout both lungs, with mild basilar predominance [37]. Normal radiographic findings in the early stages of disease are well recognized and occur in 25%–40% of persons at initial presentation [37–39]; typical miliary lesions may not be visible until 3–6 weeks after hematogenous dissemination [39]. Bronchiectasis and residual cavities are sequelae of pulmonary TB that typically involve the upper lobes [26, 36]. Rasmussen aneurysm is a pseudoaneurysm of a pulmonary artery caused by erosion from an adjacent tuberculous cavity. Broncholithiasis is an uncommon complication.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the radiographic findings in lower lung field TB differ significantly from upper lobe disease. The most frequent radiographic finding is consolidation, more confluent and extensive than that found in upper lobes TB. Cavitory lesions are also frequently seen, which may be single or multiple and may lie within an area of consolidation. Other radiological features include evidence of atelectasis or solitary mass with intrathoracic lymphadenopathy.

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